

Privacy Considerations of Artificial Intelligence Scribes

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence (AI) scribes are increasingly deployed in United States health systems to document patient–physician encounters, with anticipated gains in administrative efficiency counterbalanced by emerging privacy risks. These systems capture audio of clinical encounters and generate transcripts and structured clinical notes, yet vendor practices differ substantially in how long each data type is retained and whether it is used for AI training. Federal and state privacy frameworks govern the collection, storage, and disclosure of such data, shaping institutional obligations and constraints. Effective implementation therefore depends on clear governance of data flows, appropriately calibrated retention and deletion policies, and transparent consent processes that align technical design with legal requirements and ethical principles.

Description

This Policy Corner examines the emerging privacy risks related to AI scribes, outlining data flows and key privacy considerations, and offers best practice recommendations for health systems implementing or considering their use.

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Hospitals and clinics in the United States (U.S.) are rapidly adopting “scribes” powered by artificial intelligence (AI) to capture patient–physician encounters and draft clinical notes. Although scribes may reduce documentation burden and physician burnout,^{1,2} they also raise important data privacy considerations.

In this Perspective, we describe the typical workflow of AI scribes, including the types of data collected at each stage. We then examine key privacy considerations and provide recommendations for health systems that are adopting or currently using these tools. We focus on U.S. law due to the rapid adoption of scribes and investment in AI, but our analysis may also be relevant to hospitals outside the U.S. navigating similar technology adoption and related privacy issues.

AI Scribes and Data Handling

AI scribes record the patient–physician conversation, typically through a microphone integrated into the physician’s mobile device. Next, they usually create a transcript of the entire conversation and generate a summary as a clinical note for the physician to review. The physician can edit the note or approve it without edits for inclusion in the patient’s medical record.^{3,4}

In the process, AI scribes generate several types of data: (1) the audio recording, (2) the AI-generated transcript of the patient–physician encounter, and (3) the unedited AI-generated clinical note (i.e., the summary of the encounter); and, depending on whether the physician makes edits to the clinical note, (4) the human-edited AI-generated clinical note. The AI-generated clinical note, whether edited by the physician or not, will be approved by the physician and included in the patient’s medical record.

Although AI scribes are becoming more common, there is no universally recognized, harmonized standard which governs their data handling practices. Some vendors, such as Nabla, use Google Cloud Platform and Microsoft Azure for data processing and “store transcripts and notes temporarily,” typically for 14 days, but do not retain audio recordings, which are processed in “chunks” and then discarded.⁵ The retention period enables physicians to review the AI-generated clinical note, make edits if needed, and export it to the Electronic Health Record (EHR) software.⁵ If not deactivated by organizations, physicians can also optionally send feedback to Nabla, including uploading the AI-generated transcript and note.⁵ However, such feedback data is permanently stored and used for support and AI training.⁵ Thus, before using it for such purposes, Nabla deploys a de-identification algorithm to remove personally identifiable information in the transcript and note.⁵

Other AI scribes, such as Tali AI, store audio for up to 48 hours and transcripts and notes for at least 30 days.⁶ Upheal, meanwhile, deletes audio recordings immediately after processing (unless the patient’s consent is obtained), but transcripts and notes are retained, unless the provider chooses to delete them.⁷ An overview of different data retention policies for AI scribes is provided in Table 1.

Vendor	Audio Recording	AI-Generated Transcript	AI-Generated Clinical Note	AI Training
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Freed AI ⁸	Not stored; immediate deletion after note generation (within 60 seconds)	Not specified	Retained by default (user can enable auto-deletion after 30 days or delete manually at any time)	Yes (training on de-identified notes; PHI excluded from training)
Heidi Health ⁹	Not stored	Customizable by users and organizations (minimum: 1 day; default “never delete”)	Deletion of draft possible once included in the patient’s medical record	No use of sensitive health information
Microsoft Dragon Copilot ¹⁰	Retained up to 90 days	Retained up to 90 days	Not specified	Yes (Use of de-identified data)
Nabla ⁵	Not retained; processed in “chunks” and then discarded	Stored temporarily (default 14 days)	Stored temporarily (default 14 days)	Optional (de-identified transcripts and notes from physician feedback)
Suki ¹¹	Deleted after 30 days	Deleted after 30 days	Final note retained for the duration of the service contract	Yes (de-identified data, including de-identified audio and transcript)
Sunoh.ai ¹²	Deleted automatically after seven days	Deleted automatically after seven days	Final note retained in the EHR database	PHI/PII not used to train AI models
Tali AI ⁶	Stored for up to 48 hours	Retained for at least 30 days	AI-generated draft note retained for at least 30 days	Yes (de-identified transcripts and notes may be used for product and service improvement)
Upheal ⁷	Deleted immediately after processing (default); exception:	Retained (optional deletion by provider)	Approved note retained but may be deleted once submitted to insurance; providers must	Optional (for AI/product improvement; de-identified transcripts stored 1 year; de-identified derived

	patient consent		typically retain for 6-7 years	datasets stored 5 years)
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Table 1. Data Retention Policies for AI Scribes

In general, audio retention periods vary across vendors. For example, Freed AI does not store the audio recording and deletes it immediately after note generation “within 60 seconds.”⁸ On the other side of the range is Microsoft Dragon Copilot, which retains the audio for up to 90 days.¹⁰

Transcript and clinical note retention periods are generally longer and more variable. For example, Microsoft Dragon Copilot retains transcripts for up to 90 days.¹⁰ Suki, on the other hand, deletes the transcripts after 30 days and retains the final clinical note for the duration of the service contract.¹¹ Heidi Health, meanwhile, allows users and organizations to customize transcript retention, ranging from a minimum of 1 day to indefinite retention, with “never delete” as the default setting.⁹ Finally, Sunoh.ai deletes transcripts automatically after seven days, while the finalized clinical note is stored in the EHR database.¹² It is also worth noting that vendor retention policies generally do not clearly distinguish between the unedited AI-generated clinical note and the physician-approved finalized clinical note that becomes part of the patient’s medical record, and often seem to refer to the latter.

AI training practices also differ in whether participation is default or optional. Across vendors that use data for AI training, a consistent practice appears to be the use of de-identified data only, with Protected Health Information (PHI) explicitly excluded. Notably, not all vendors publicly disclose retention policy practices for all data categories. For example, Abridge’s data retention and AI training policies for clinical encounter data are governed exclusively by private contracts and business associate agreements, with no publicly available information.¹³ Table 1 illustrates vendor-specific differences in public disclosure of retention policies and the optional nature of participation in AI training.

Together, these findings suggest that hospitals and health systems face important choices both when selecting and implementing an AI scribe: whether to retain the audio recording, transcript, and clinical note — and if so, by whom, where, and for how long? Each choice comes with tradeoffs.

Privacy Considerations

Privacy law influences how health systems answer these questions. The main federal privacy law in the U.S., the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA), applies to “covered entities,” which includes most hospitals and physicians. Because it regulates the use and disclosure of PHI, which is “individually identifiable health information” created or received by covered entities or their business associates, HIPAA can apply to certain data created or received by AI scribe vendors (45 C.F.R. §§ 160.102,

160.103), including voice recordings, transcripts, and clinical notes when they involve individually identifiable health information (e.g., a patient’s symptoms and diagnosis).³

HIPAA provides protection for PHI use and disclosure, but does not specify minimum or maximum retention periods for medical records. However, some protections do exist. For example, HIPAA requires “appropriate administrative, technical, and physical safeguards” for the protection of the privacy of PHI, including during storage and disposal (45 C.F.R. § 164.530(c)). Additionally, Medicare regulations require that hospitals retain medical records “in their original or legally reproduced form for a period of at least 5 years” (42 C.F.R. § 482.24(b)). The content of a medical record “must contain information to justify admission and continued hospitalization, support the diagnosis, and describe the patient’s progress and response to medications and services” (42 C.F.R. § 482.24(c)). Consequently, while physician-approved AI-generated clinical notes are part of the medical record because they support a patient’s diagnosis or constitute a progress note and thus must be retained for 5 years, audio recordings and transcripts likely fall outside the term “medical record” for Medicare purposes unless the hospital uses them as documentation of care. Finally, state medical records retention laws usually require retention periods between 5 and 10 years for adult patients.¹⁴ Most states do not define the term “medical record” in their retention laws, though some specify content requirements that closely parallel Medicare regulations.¹⁵

State privacy laws also affect how health systems respond. These include modern consumer data protection statutes such as the California Consumer Privacy Act, as well as wiretapping laws and laws protecting confidentiality. For example, in *Saucedo v. Sharp Healthcare et al.*, 25-CU-063632C (Cal. Sup. Ct., Nov. 26, 2025), a patient sued a healthcare system using an AI scribe without his consent for violating a variety of California state privacy laws, including a criminal statute that allows private parties to bring claims for money damages. The allegations included transmitting confidential communications to third-party vendors, failing to implement “deletion-on-demand” capabilities, and allowing third-party access and retention, all without his consent.

Best Practice Recommendations

As discussed above, to comply with federal or state laws, health systems may not need to retain the audio recording or transcript for very long — or at all — provided they are not treated as part of the patient’s medical record. However, health systems are increasingly using medical record data, which includes the physician-approved AI-generated clinical notes, for additional uses: for research, to improve healthcare operations, and to potentially develop new technologies.^{2,4} Health systems may also wish to continually assess the performance of AI scribes to ensure they perform reliably and accurately, rather than rely solely on manufacturer data, as well as analyze physicians’ behavior to evaluate the tools’ benefits. For such purposes, health systems may wish to retain audio recordings and transcripts for a longer period as a form of “ground truth” for internal evaluation and validation.

This creates a tension between the most privacy-protective approach for patients (i.e., deletion immediately after generation of the clinical note) and the interests of health systems in retaining recordings and transcripts for research purposes. However, there are ways to balance these competing interests. For instance, if the transcript is human-validated (which is increasingly less common among newer AI scribes), the audio recording could be deleted immediately after validation as a best practice since, at that point, it is no longer needed as a form of “ground truth.” Additionally, to maximize data protection, the transcript could then be de-identified, such as by removing HIPAA’s 18 identifiers (45 C.F.R. § 164.514(a)-(b)), if those identifiers are no longer needed. De-identified information is no longer PHI and can generally be shared with third parties without HIPAA restrictions, including with scholars for research purposes or with companies for AI development (45 C.F.R. § 164.502(d)(2)). In contrast, keeping the audio recording and de-identifying it remains technically challenging, requiring specialized technology to distort or alter the voice in addition to removing identifiers.³

However, risks remain even with de-identified information since third parties may be able to re-identify individuals with little additional information.³ Health systems should therefore carefully assess such risks and include re-identification bans in data use agreements. When complete de-identification is uncertain, health systems can consider sharing PHI that excludes certain direct identifiers with a data use agreement as “limited data sets” (45 C.F.R. § 164.514(e)) instead of risking HIPAA violations.¹⁶ However, HIPAA generally prohibits the sale of PHI (45 C.F.R. §§ 164.502(a)(5)(ii), 164.508(a)(4)). Recent case law shows that sharing PHI with companies in exchange for a nonexclusive, perpetual license to use any AI tool developed with such data can violate this ban without obtaining prior written patient authorization.¹⁶

In general, health systems should develop data governance policies for AI scribes that comply with applicable federal and state laws and clearly specify data collection, storage, access, sharing, retention, and deletion for different data types. In this context, health systems should also assess their technical capabilities and resources when selecting an AI scribe, considering whether to store the data in the AI scribe provider’s cloud or locally. Having a clear vision of the preferred data handling practice will also help HIPAA-covered entities when entering into a business associate agreement under HIPAA with an AI scribe provider and when negotiating its terms to appropriately safeguard PHI (45 C.F.R. §§ 164.502(e), 164.504(e)).

Health systems should also ensure that their privacy practices adequately inform patients about data use and obtain consent to recording under applicable state wiretapping and privacy laws.³ No matter what the law requires, best practice should be to inform patients about the use of AI scribes and explain in plain language what data is collected, for what purposes, and how it is protected. This information should be provided to patients orally and in writing, with a clear opt-out option that they can select outside the clinician’s

presence. Health systems might also consider having patients watch a short video that explains the AI scribe process before each encounter.³

Lastly, health systems should train procurement teams, deployment teams, and clinicians on how to select and use AI scribes in compliance with applicable laws. This includes ensuring that the scribe's technical and workflow functionalities align with state and federal requirements for consent and privacy, and that these legal requirements are incorporated into formal organizational workflows. Health systems should also closely monitor changes in state law, particularly those that may expand the definition of medical records or introduce new categories of protected information.

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Conflicts of interest

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